

Lorentz Invariant $-EE + ppcc = -mocc$, Orthogonal States and Spin $\frac{1}{2}$

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Dec 17, 2024

Dirac obtained spin matrices for spin $\frac{1}{2}$ by linearizing the Klein-Gordon equation. This equation, in turn, is obtained by using quantum mechanical ideas, i.e. replacing E with $i\partial/\partial t$ partial and p with $-i \text{ grad}$ in the Lorentz invariant $-EE + ppcc = -mocc$ ((1))

In this note, we try to argue that the notion of quantum mechanics and spin are present in ((1)). In (1), we argued that quantum mechanics is linked to entangled states which may contain information about classical probabilities. In particular, we argued that a photon or particle may pass through one slit or the other of a 2-slit apparatus and yet interact with both creating an entangled state. (This occurs if \hbar/p is of the order of the slit widths/separations.) This entangled state should contain information about the probability to pass through one slit or the other and so may be written as $|\text{slit } 1\rangle + |\text{slit } 2\rangle$ ((2)). Here the weights are equal. This wavefunction is a physical entangled state (not a probabilistic one like a coin which may be heads or tails). In (1), it was argued that $|\text{slit } 1\rangle$ and $|\text{slit } 2\rangle$ must be orthogonal functions and that one must take the square of ((2)) (dot product or integral over x,y) in order to obtain a positive function which describes classical probability. In other words, (1) argues that squaring (dot product) and orthogonality go hand-in-hand in quantum mechanics.

Here, we argue that $EE = ppcc + momoccc$ follows the same mathematical formalism. It is a square and involves two orthogonal states $mocc$ and pc . In other words, one could write $E \text{ vector} = pc \text{ xunit} + mocc \text{ yunit}$. The issue is that $xunit$ and $yunit$ do not correspond to any vectors in 3-space and so if one wishes to only have physical vectors, one must replace $xunit$ vector and y unit vector with operators (matrices) and this gives rise to the notion of spin $.5$ (we argue). (This, however, requires 4×4 matrices a Dirac already showed in the 1920s.)

Quantum Mechanics, Entangled and Classical States and Orthogonality

In (1), we argued that quantum mechanics differs from classical mechanics in that it contains entangled states. These are physical states (not mathematical probabilistic states like $.5$ heads $+ .5$ tails for a tossed coin). The physical entangled state, however, could contain information about a related classical probability.

In particular, (1) argues that 2-slit interference/diffraction is one such example. If \hbar/p is of the order of the slit widths/separations then an entangled state is created because the particle interacts with both slits even though it only passes through one or the other. Thus, one has the classical probability to pass through one state or the other, but physically, an entangled state.

In (1) it is argued that the entangled state may be described mathematically by $F1(x,y) + F2(x,y)$ where $F1$ is a function associated with slit 1 and $F2$, with slit 2. It is argued that $F1$ and $F2$ must be both positive and negative to create an entangled physical state. If they were both positive this would be the usual classical probabilistic state of $.5$ heads $+ .5$ tails, which is not a physical state. This, however, forces one to square $F1 + F2$ in order to obtain a positive number which is necessary for classical probability. This yields the intensity probability in x,y . If one wishes to find the probability to pass through one slit or the other, it is argued that one must integrate over x,y

and that F_1 and F_2 must be orthogonal. We note that mathematically integration $\int dx dy F_1(x,y)F_2(x,y)$ is a form of dot product (linear algebra).

Thus the quantum prescription, at least according to (1), seems to involve a sum of orthogonal functions and squaring and integrating (taking a dot product). We argue that this exact recipe/formalism seems to exist for the Lorentz invariant: $-E^2 + pcpc = -m_0^2 c^4$ ((3))

We first note that one sees squared terms which matches the notion of squaring. The orthogonality may be seen by writing E as a vector:

$$E \text{ vector} = pc(x \text{ unit vector}) + m_0 c^2 (y \text{ unit vector}) \quad ((4))$$

This begs at least two questions. First, why are the variables p, E and m_0 used and secondly, why introduce orthogonal vectors? The Lorentz invariant ((3)) may be obtained from considerations of a Lorentz transformation acting on $(p=0, m_0 c^2)$ and (x, ct) , but here we argue that E, m_0 and p are measurable quantities. m_0 may be measured by an inertial approach in the rest frame and p , by an impulse hit against a target. Thus, one has a state E which is linked to two measurable quantities, but is a kind of entangled state of both (so to speak). We next note that p only exists in a frame moving with $-v$, while m_0 exists in the rest frame. Thus, there are two distinct frames, like the two slits and we argue that they should be distinguished by being orthogonal in terms of a dot product. This explains the presence of $(x \text{ unit vector})$ and $(y \text{ unit vector})$.

Thus, we argue that the Lorentz invariant ((3)) is really in the same mathematical form as quantum formalism for two slit interference/diffraction. One has an entangled state (E vector) linked with two states p and m_0 (taken to be orthogonal to distinguish them) and one must take a dot product and have orthogonality so that one has mutually exclusive probability, here energy squared.

The Notion of Spin $\frac{1}{2}$

((4)) uses two unit vectors and there is no notion of spin. We argue, however, that physically, vectors exist in 3-space and so it is not clear what $(x \text{ unit vector})$ and $(y \text{ unit vector})$ mean in ((4)). They are abstract vectors and so do not seem to have a physical grounding. We suggest that they may be replaced by operators (matrices) which achieve the same goal, namely make p and m_0 orthogonal. First of all, one may note that in general, p is a vector (p_x, p_y, p_z) and so one would need three matrices, one for each, which anticommute so that squaring leads to $p_x p_x + p_y p_y + p_z p_z$. The 2x2 Pauli matrices fit this condition. The real issue, however, is to have p and m_0 be orthogonal. This requirement may be changed slightly by writing E and p on the LHS and m_0 on the RHS side. In such a case one wishes to have no cross terms between E and p . This leads to:

$$\text{Matrix linked to } E \begin{vmatrix} I & 0 \\ 0 & -I \end{vmatrix} \quad \text{Here } I \text{ is the } 2 \times 2 \text{ identity matrix} \quad ((5a))$$

The p matrices are:
$$\begin{vmatrix} 0 & \sigma(i) \\ -\sigma(i) & 0 \end{vmatrix} \quad ((5b))$$

Here $\sigma(x)$, $\sigma(y)$, $\sigma(z)$ are the three Pauli matrices. One may see that they anticommute with ((5a)). Thus, orthogonality is achieved through anticommutation in the case of matrices here instead of a usual dot product.

The ((5b)) matrices are associated with 4-vectors which represent two spinors associated with spin up-spin down, i.e. with spin $\frac{1}{2}$. These 4-vectors were already obtained by Dirac in the 1920s, but we argue that the quantum formalism is already present in $-EE + pcpc = -m^2c^2$, even if one does not consider $E \rightarrow \text{id}/dt$ partial and $p \rightarrow -i \text{ grad}$. In other words, considerations of the mathematical formalism linked to 2-slit interference/diffraction seems to show that $-EE + pcpc = -m^2c^2$ is of the same form and so could also represent quantum mechanics. In fact, if one writes $E \text{ vector} + p \text{ vector} = m_0 \text{ vector}$ such that one has orthogonality and replaces the vectors with matrices, then the notion of quantum spin (spin .5) arises.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that following (1), a quantum entangled (physical state) may contain elements (information) about classical probabilities. For example, a photon/particle interacting with a 2-slit system with slit width/separations of the order of \hbar/p interacts with both creating a physical entangled state, but there is still the classical probability associated with passing through one slit or the other. According to (1), one may write $F_1(x,y) + F_2(x,y)$ where 1 and 2 represent slit 1 and slit 2, but these cannot be positive functions, otherwise they could be interpreted as simply the addition of probabilities as in the case of a tossed coin. One must have a physical ,entangled state. This implies F_1 and F_2 being both positive and negative and the same result for their sum. Thus, one must square $F_1 + F_2$ to obtain a positive function which could represent probability. To obtain information only about slit 1 or 2, one must integrate over x,y and $\int dx dy F_1 F_2 = 0$, i.e. F_1 and F_2 must be orthogonal. Note: An integral is a dot product.

We suggest that the same formalism seems to be present in the Lorentz invariant $-EE + pcpc = -m^2c^2$. This is a squared equation which uses physical measurables p and m_0 . Thus, $E \text{ vector} = pc (\text{unit } x \text{ vector}) + m_0 c (\text{unit } y \text{ vector})$ seems to represent an entangled state. Squaring requires orthogonal (through a dot product) so p and m_0 remain mutually exclusive because they are associated with different physical frames. m_0 represents a rest frame while p requires a moving one. One may alternatively write $E (\text{unit vector } 1) + p (\text{unit vector } 2) = m_0 \text{ vector } 3$.

Now we argue that there are no physical unit vectors present. Vectors here exist in 3-space and so we suggest that one replace the unit vectors with matrices. In general, p is represented by p_x, p_y, p_z and so 2x2 Pauli matrices which anticommute produce $p_x p_x + p_y p_y + p_z p_z$. One, however, requires 4x4 Dirac matrices (described above) to make a matrix associated with E anticommute with one associated with p . This then leads to a 4-vector consisting of 2 spinors, or spin $\frac{1}{2}$ physics. (Here m_0 becomes associated with a unit matrix.)

Reference

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Mutual Exclusivity in Classical Probability and Related Information in Entangled States (preprint, zenodo, 2024)
2. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Gamma_matrices